

Kinetics and Mechanism of Osmium Tetroxide catalysed Oxidation of Benzilic Acid by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III)

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Kinetics of osmium tetroxide catalysed oxidation of benzilic acid by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) have been studied in 30% (v/v) t-butanol—water mixture at a constant ionic strength. The reaction is found to be first order each in [substrate], $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ and $[\text{OH}^-]$ but independent of [hexacyanoferrate(III)]. The rate of reaction decreases with the decrease in dielectric constant and increases with increase in ionic strength of the medium. The entropy of activation is found to be negative. The mechanism involves the formation of an intermediate complex between the acid anion and Os^{VIII} , which rapidly decomposes followed by a fast reaction between the reduced osmium species and hexacyanoferrate(III).

IN continuation of our earlier work¹, the kinetics of osmium tetroxide catalysed oxidation of benzilic acid by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) are reported herein. The uncatalysed oxidation of benzilic acid by hexacyanoferrate(III) is either extremely slow or does not proceed at all. In the presence of a catalyst, like Os^{VIII} , this reaction is amenable to kinetic investigation.

Experimental

Benzilic acid (extra pure, Fluka), t-butanol, hexacyanoferrate(III), potassium chloride and potassium hydroxide (all AnalaR) were used. The solution of osmium tetroxide ($0.004 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) was prepared by dissolving OsO_4 (Johnson and Mathey) in KOH solution (0.05 mol dm^{-3}). Ionic strength was adjusted with potassium chloride.

Kinetic measurement: Reaction mixture containing the requisite quantities of benzilic acid, OsO_4 and KOH, and a solution of hexacyanoferrate(III) were thermally equilibrated separately for about 30 min at 30° . A known volume of hexacyanoferrate(III) was then transferred to the reaction mixture and aliquots were removed at regular time intervals, and the amount of hexacyanoferrate(II) formed during the reaction was estimated by titrating against a standard solution of ceric salt using ferroin as an indicator. The standard zero order rate constants (k_o) reported are average values of duplicate runs. No oxidation of the solvent occurred under the experimental conditions.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry: Stoichiometric investigation carried out using a known excess of hexacyano-

ferrate(III) at 30° , showed that 1 mol of benzilic acid required 2 mol of hexacyanoferrate(III) to give benzophenone² as the final product of oxidation. The yield of the product was found to be 60%. The product was characterised by direct comparison (m.m.p., ir spectra) with an authentic sample of benzophenone, m.p. and m.m.p. 48.1° .

Rate laws: The reaction is zero order in [hexacyanoferrate(III)] as shown by the constant values of k_o over a ten-fold variation of [hexacyanoferrate(III)] (Table 1). The rate of the reaction increases with the increase in [benzilic acid] (Table 2), indicating the first order reaction with respect to benzilic acid. The oxidation rate is directly proportional to [alkali] (Table 3) at low $[\text{OH}^-]$ ($< 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) but it becomes zero order at $[\text{OH}^-] > 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The rate of the reaction increases with the increase in catalyst concentration (Table 4). The values of $k_o/[\text{OsO}_4]$ are found to be increased at low catalyst concentration

TABLE 1 — DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [HEXACYANOFERRATE(III)]

[Benzilic acid] = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{OH}^-] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 30° , $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Solvent: 30% (v/v) t-butanol

[Hexacyanoferrate(III)] $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	k_o $\times 10^5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$
1.0	7.94
2.0	7.90
4.0	7.75
6.0	7.73
8.0	7.50
10.0	7.90

TABLE 2 - DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [BENZILIC ACID]

[Hexacyanoferrate(III)] = 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [OsO₄] = 1.55×10^{-7} mol dm⁻³, [OH⁻] = 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, $\mu = 0.1$ mol dm⁻², Temp. = 30°, Solvent : 30% (v/v) t-butanol

[Benzilic acid] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	k _o × 10 ⁵ mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	k _o (× 10 ⁵ min ⁻¹) / [Benzilic acid]
1.0	1.58	1.58
2.0	3.10	1.50
4.0	6.23	1.55
5.0	7.94	1.58
8.0	12.24	1.53
10.0	15.63	1.56

TABLE 3 - DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [OH⁻]

[Hexacyanoferrate(III)] = 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [OsO₄] = 1.55×10^{-7} mol dm⁻³, [Benzilic acid] = 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, $\mu = 0.1$ mol dm⁻², Temp. = 30°, Solvent : 30% (v/v) t-butanol

[OH ⁻] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	k _o × 10 ⁵ mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹
1.0	3.57
2.0	7.94
4.0	16.43
6.0	22.81
8.0	29.60
10.0	38.01
12.0	38.03
14.0	38.01
15.0	37.88

TABLE 4 - DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [OsO₄]

[Hexacyanoferrate(III)] = 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [Benzilic acid] = 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [OH⁻] = 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, $\mu = 0.1$ mol dm⁻², Temp. = 30°, Solvent : 30% (v/v) tertiary butanol

[OsO ₄] × 10 ⁷ mol dm ⁻³	k _o × 10 ⁵ mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	k _o (× 10 ⁵ min ⁻¹) / [OsO ₄]
1.0	5.10	0.51
1.5	7.94	0.53
2.5	13.43	0.53
3.5	18.94	0.54
5.0	27.05	0.54
6.0	33.61	0.56
7.0	38.73	0.55
10.0	54.01	0.54
12.0	63.60	0.53
14.0	72.78	0.52
15.0	75.01	0.50

(< 6.0×10^{-7} mol dm⁻³) but at high catalyst concentrations the values decrease. However, to the first approximation, the direct proportionality of the reaction rate at low catalyst concentration might be assumed. The rate of the reaction increases with the increase in ionic strength of the medium, and a plot of log k_o vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ is linear (Fig. 1), indicating ion ion reaction. Added ferrocyanide showed no effect on the rate of oxidation.

Solvent effect: The decrease in the dielectric constant (D) of the medium decreases the rate constant, and the plot of log k_o vs 1/D of the

medium is linear (Fig. 2) which provides an additional evidence in favour of ion-ion reaction.

Fig. 1. Effect of ionic strength on rate; [Hexacyanoferrate(III)] = 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [Benzilic acid] = 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [OsO₄] = 1.5×10^{-7} mol dm⁻³, [OH⁻] = 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, temp. = 30°, solvent = 30% (v/v) t-butanol.

Fig. 2. Effect of dielectric constant on rate; [Hexacyanoferrate(III)] = 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [Benzilic acid] = 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [OH⁻] = 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [OsO₄] = 1.5×10^{-7} mol dm⁻³, $\mu = 0.1$ mol dm⁻²; temp. = 30°.

Effects of temperature: The plot of log k_o vs 1/T is linear. The energies of activation, entropies of activation and enthalpies of activations are found to be 31.99 ± 2.5 KJ mol⁻¹, -224.56 ± 3.3 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹ and 31.37 ± 2.4 KJ mol⁻¹ respectively. At 30°, 35° and 45°, the values of k_o (× 10⁵ mol dm⁻³ min⁻¹) are 7.94, 12.30 and 17.40 respectively.

The osmium tetroxide catalysed oxidation of benzilic acid by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) is characterised by the following facts. (i) The

reaction rate is independent of the initial concentration of hexacyanoferrate(III), but proportional to concentration of benzilic acid, alkali and osmium tetroxide. (ii) The rate of the reaction decreases with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium. (iii) The reaction velocity increases with the increase in ionic strength of the medium. (iv) The entropy of activation is found to be negative. (v) The stoichiometry of the reaction was calculated to be 2 : 1 Δ hexacyanoferrate(III)/ Δ benzilic acid, and the product of oxidation was found to be benzophenone.

Thus under the above conditions, a probable rate law might be given as

$$-d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]/dt = k[\text{benzilic acid}] \times [\text{OH}^-][\text{OsO}_4]$$

In the present investigation, no induced polymerisation of acrylonitrile or reduction of HgCl_2 has been observed. Hence a free radical mechanism is ruled out. But on the other hand, the reaction is alkali dependent, shows positive salt effect, is sensitive to changes in dielectric constant, and the entropy of activation is negative. The reaction probably proceeds through an ionic mechanism involving an acid anion intermediate.

Benzilic acid is easily oxidised⁸ to benzophenone by $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$. The redox potential of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}/2\text{SO}_4^{2-}$ couple is 2.01 V which is high enough to oxidise the substrate. The oxidation of the same substrate by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) on the other hand, does not proceed in the absence of the catalyst. This is possibly because the oxidation potential of hexacyanoferrate(III)/hexacyanoferrate(II) couple is very low (-0.36 V) and does not appear to differ appreciably from that of benzilic acid/benzophenone couple, the data for which are lacking in the literature. However, the oxidising or reducing ability of a substance can be altered by diminishing the activity of the oxidised or the reduced form of the redox couple and this can be achieved by the addition of a suitable complexing agent. The catalyst osmium tetroxide which is necessary to promote the reaction, possibly plays a role in lowering the redox potential of benzilic acid/benzophenone couple.

It is worthwhile to mention that if only benzilic acid and OsO_4 are taken in alkaline medium, the colour of the osmium tetroxide immediately disappears and if this solution is acidified and titrated against standard ceric sulphate solution, then 2 mole of ceric ions are required for one mole of OsO_4 . This proves that it is the reduced osmium which is first oxidised to its original octavalent state by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III). It has already been pointed out that the oxidation of benzilic acid with ceric sulphate is not appreciable under these conditions and hence it is possibly the Os^{VI} which reacts rapidly with hexacyanoferrate(III) ion. The alkali dependence of the oxidation process clearly indicates that the oxidation of benzilic acid takes place through the formation of a complex

anion between OsO_4 and OH^- ion. Since the uncatalysed oxidation does not proceed at all and hexacyanoferrate(III) is consumed without taking part in the rate law, it is assumed that hexacyanoferrate(III) does not react directly until after the rate-determining step. It is the reduced osmium which is first oxidised to its original octavalent state. Further, according to the proposed rate law, the rate-determining step involves the interaction between two negatively charged ions or between a negatively charged ion and a polar molecule and thus should correspond to a negative entropy change⁹.

A mechanism based on formation of a soluble complex between acid anion and Os^{VII} is suggested. Benzophenone as the product of oxidation has been isolated.

For the reaction involving interaction between similarly charged ions, the plot of $\log k_0$ vs $1/D$ should be a straight line having a negative slope. In the present investigation, similar results have been obtained (Fig. 2).

The mechanism proposed involves formation of a complex between acid anion and Os^{VII} . This complex then decomposes to give benzophenone, and Os^{VII} ion is then regenerated by the oxidation of Os^{VI} by two molecules of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion.

More negative value of $\Delta S^\ddagger$ than expected supports equation (2) as the rate-determining step that is the slow step, as two ions combine to give a bigger complex ion resulting thereby in the loss of freedom of motion. Positive salt-effect further lends support to the mechanistic steps, suggesting reaction between two similar charges. On the basis of this mechanism and applying steady state approximation, we get,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= -\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}}{dt} \\ &= \frac{k_2 k_3 [\text{benzilic acid}] [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] [\text{OH}^-]}{k_{-2} + k_3 [\text{OH}^-]} \\ &= \frac{k_2 [\text{benzilic acid}] [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] [\text{OH}^-]}{\frac{k_{-2}}{k_3} + [\text{OH}^-]} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Assuming $[\text{OH}^-]$ to be low, such that $k_{-2}/k_3 > [\text{OH}^-]$ and $\{k_{-2}/k_3 + [\text{OH}^-]\} \approx k_{-2}/k_3$, the rate law (5) approximates to equation (6).

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_2 k_3}{k_{-2}} [\text{benzilic acid}] [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] [\text{OH}^-] \quad (6)$$

At high $[\text{OH}^-]$, $[\text{OH}^-] \gg k_{-2}/k_3$

Such that $\{k_{-2}/k_3 + [\text{OH}^-]\} \approx [\text{OH}^-]$

The rate law (5) reduces to rate law (7),

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \frac{k_2 [\text{benzilic acid}] [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] [\text{OH}^-]}{[\text{OH}^-]} \\ &= k_2 [\text{benzilic acid}] [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Thus equations (6) and (7) explain the experimental results, i.e. first order and zero order dependence of the rate on $[\text{OH}^-]$ at low and high $[\text{OH}^-]$ respectively.

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References

1. R. C. MOHAPATRA and N. C. KHANDUAL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, 21, 167, 517; P. MISHRA, R. C. MOHAPATRA and N. C. KHANDUAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 63, 291; P. MISHRA and N. C. KHANDUAL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, 25, 902
2. N. C. KHANDUAL and P. L. NAYAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 786.
3. K. S. SUKLA, P. C. MATHUR and O. P. BANSAL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, 35, 1301; V. LAL, U. N. SINGH, H. S. SINGH and M. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 329.